

The rotating reference frame with general relativity

Harald Schröder

2018

We view a rotating reference frame with constant angular velocity $(0,0,\omega)$. C shall be the light velocity in vacuum and let be x,y,z the known coordinates and t the time in the motionless reference frame. Let be $z=0$ and τ is the proper time of the rotating reference frame. At [1] p.357,358 it will be shown that this problem contains the centrifugal- and the Coriolis acceleration (terms of first order). Here we take into consideration terms of higher order: $\omega^2(x^2+y^2) \ll c^2$ see [1] (9.1)
The metric tensor can be written with [1] p.357 (A.13):

$$G = (g_{\mu\nu}) = \begin{pmatrix} (1 - \omega^2(x^2+y^2)/c^2) & (\omega y/c) & (-\omega x/c) & 0 \\ (\omega y/c) & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ (-\omega x/c) & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get the inverse matrix with [1] p.357 (A.14):

$$G^{-1} = (g^{\mu\nu}) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & (\omega y/c) & (-\omega x/c) & 0 \\ (\omega y/c)(-1 + \omega^2 y^2/c^2) & (-\omega^2 x y/c^2) & 0 & 0 \\ (-\omega x/c)(-1 + \omega^2 x^2/c^2) & (-\omega^2 x y/c^2) & (-1 + \omega^2 x^2/c^2) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Following differentiations of metric tensor are not equal to zero:

$$\frac{\partial g_{00}}{\partial x} = -\frac{2\omega^2 x}{c^2}, \quad \frac{\partial g_{00}}{\partial y} = \frac{-2\omega^2 y}{c^2}, \quad \frac{\partial g_{01}}{\partial y} = \frac{\omega}{c}, \quad \frac{\partial g_{02}}{\partial x} = -\frac{\omega}{c}$$
$$\frac{\partial g_{10}}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial g_{01}}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial g_{20}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial g_{02}}{\partial x}$$

If we use the equation of motion see [1] p.55 (11.9)

$$\frac{d^2 x^k}{d\tau^2} = - \sum_{\nu, \mu=0}^3 \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^k \cdot \left(\frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau} \right) \quad x^0 = c \cdot t$$

we get the differential equation of x-component:

$$\frac{d^2 x}{d\tau^2} = 2 \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dy}{d\tau} \right) + \omega^2 \cdot x \cdot \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right)^2$$

with Christoffel symbols (see formula (11.18) on p.57 in [1]):

$$\Gamma_{00}^1 = - \frac{\omega^2 x}{c^2} \quad \Gamma_{02}^1 = - \frac{\omega}{c}$$

We yield the differential equation of y-component:

$$\frac{d^2 y}{d\tau^2} = \left(1 - \frac{\omega^2 x^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot \omega^2 y \cdot \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right)^2 - 2\omega \cdot \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dx}{d\tau} \right)$$

with Christoffel symbols:

$$\Gamma_{00}^2 = \frac{\omega^2 y}{c^2} \cdot \left(\frac{\omega^2 x^2}{c^2} - 1 \right) \quad \Gamma_{01}^2 = \frac{\omega}{c}$$

The differential equation of transformed time can be written as:

$$- \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2} = \frac{4\omega^2 x}{c^2} \cdot \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dx}{d\tau} \right)$$

To z-component we get $\frac{d^2 z}{d\tau^2} = 0$ This is no contradiction to $z=0$.

We can choose suitable initial position and initial velocity, we get an initial value problem.

Literature:

[1] = Torsten Fließbach „Allgemeine Relativitätstheorie“ Springer Spektrum 6. Edition 2012